

Elsevier Editorial System(tm) for Consciousness and Cognition
Manuscript Draft

Manuscript Number: CONCOG-13-203R1

Title: Jumping to Conclusions bias, BADE and Feedback Sensitivity in Schizophrenia and Schizotypy

Article Type: Regular Article

Keywords: Jumping To Conclusions, pictures to decision task, Schizophrenia, Schizotypy, Feedback Sensitivity, BADE

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Abstract: Several studies about schizophrenia have shown a cognitive bias named "Jumping to conclusions". The main objective of this study is to compare JTC bias and BADE (Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence) in patients with schizophrenia versus high/low schizotypy groups. We used a modified version of DTD task. In addition to the traditional parameters of it, we calculated accuracy and Feedback Sensitivity which lower scores shows greater use of feedback. The results suggest that patients were less sensitive to feedback. In the cued condition, the control groups made better use of feedback. In the uncued condition, we found JTC bias at stage 1 only for patients and high schizotypy participants. PR at first stages related positively with FS and negatively with accuracy too. BADE seems unrelated to JTC bias and FS. The results are discussed in terms of JTC as a clinical bias and whether patients are less able to use feedback.

Jumping to Conclusions bias, BADE and Feedback

Sensitivity in Schizophrenia and Schizotypy

Abstract

Several studies about schizophrenia have shown a cognitive bias named "Jumping to conclusions" (JTC), defined as a decision made quickly on the basis of little evidence that occurs in these patients when performing probabilistic reasoning paradigms. The main objective of this study is to compare JTC bias and BADE (Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence) in patients with schizophrenia versus participants with high/low schizotypy to understand the underlying mechanism of these cognitive biases. Probabilistic reasoning was assessed using a modified version of Drawing to Decision task. In addition to the traditional parameters of this task (Plausibility Rating (PR), Draws to Decision (DTD), BADE) we also calculated new parameters, overall accuracy and one named Feedback Sensitivity (FS) which lower scores shows greater use of feedback. The results of the study suggest that patients with schizophrenia were less sensitive to feedback than the two groups of high/low schizotypy participants. In the cued condition, the control groups made better use of feedback and showed more plausibility and accuracy in the last stages. In the uncued condition, we found JTC bias at stage 1 only for patients and high schizotypy participants. At the same time, PR at first stages (1 to 4) related positively with Feedback Sensitivity and negatively with accuracy for patients and high schizotypy participants (high confidence is associated with worse performance and lower feedback use). BADE seems unrelated to JTC bias and FS. The results are discussed in terms of JTC as a clinical bias and whether patients with schizophrenia are less able to use feedback.

Keywords: Jumping To Conclusions, pictures to decision task, Schizophrenia, Schizotypy, Feedback Sensitivity, BADE.

1. Introduction

Schizophrenia onset is associated with gene–environment interplay (Van Os, Kenis & Rutten, 2010). Heritability, as an index of genetic influence, must be viewed in the context of interaction with environmental, social and cognitive effects. Schizophrenia research has demonstrated a cognitive bias that occurs when using probabilistic reasoning paradigms like the task of beads (Huq et al., 1988). This cognitive bias has been called "Jumping to Conclusions". In particular, the "Jumping to Conclusions" bias has been observed to be accentuated in patients with delusions (Huq et al. 1988; Moritz and Woodward, 2005; Moritz et al, 2007; Speechley et al., 2010). However, the JTC bias has been also studied in different populations (Broome et al., 2007, van Dael et al., 2006, Lincoln et al., 2011), especially in non-clinical samples scoring high on a schizotypy scale (Rodier et al., 2011; Freeman, 2008; Warman, 2007; Van Dael, 2006; Balzan et al., 2012). Unlike schizophrenia, schizotypy is an aspect of normal individual variation (Johns and van Os, 2001) but characterized by similar psychopathology and cognitive disorganization (Stefanis et al., 2002). This continuity forms the basis of the dimensional view of schizophrenia (Claridge and Beech, 1995; Buchy, Woodward and Liotti, 2007). In other words, schizotypy can be considered qualitatively similar but quantitatively less severe than schizophrenia (van Os et al., 2000; Verdoux and van Os, 2002). The study of schizotypy in the general population is a relevant point in schizophrenia research that can provide us with clues to the possible etiological mechanisms underlying schizophrenia spectrum disorders, and may allow us to improve the strategies for prevention and early detection of this clinical disorder (Kwapil, Barrantes Vidal, & Silvia, 2008; Lenzenweger, 2010; Raine, 2006).

The "Jumping to Conclusions" cognitive bias occurs when there is a tendency to take decisions with a high level of haste, even taking into account, that there is little

evidence for this. Here, we study the JTC bias with a modified version of the Drawing to Decision Task (DDT: Moritz et al., 2006, Rubio et al., 2011) explained below, to distinguish its interpretative framework. We assume that our task (DDT) consists in an interplay between hypothesis and data (feedback) that marks the drawing interpretation (Levitan & LaBerge, 1991). In this context (the study of JTC bias with DDT in schizophrenia and schizotypy), two main specific questions for us are: 1. Does JTC bias affect task performance (accuracy)? Up until now accuracy was not computed in DDT. Probably this cognitive bias can help to solve easy questions sooner but what would happen in a more difficult version of the task? 2. Is JTC bias related with evidence (or feedback)? It may be that the cognitive bias only happens if there is little (low or null) evidence but could it happen also with a clear feedback, confirmatory or disconfirmatory, in relation to the hypothesis? These two questions are interrelated between them: normally higher accuracy and feedback use correlate. At the same time, these questions drove us to explore the relationship between JTC bias and the Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE) (Buchy, Woodward and Liotti, 2007; Moritz and Woodward, 2006). Are both cognitive biases different expressions of an underpinning factor (for example: low feedback sensitivity)? BADE has also been observed in patients with schizophrenia and in people with high schizotypy. The dimensional model of schizophrenia predicts unifying cognitive biases or that these cognitive biases may combine to contribute to the formation of the delusional aspects of psychosis (Buchy, Woodward and Liotti, 2007). New studies are necessary to investigate which combinations of such cognitive biases may be used to predict first episodes of psychosis. But until now the relationship between these two cognitive biases is still an open and complex question: it remains unclear whether these reasoning biases are independent or share common underpinnings (Munz, 2011). Then, another goal of

our study is to reproduce the JTC and BADE biases in patients with schizophrenia and in a non-clinical sample of participants with high (versus low) schizotypy trait, measured using the CAPE questionnaire (Stefanis et al., 2002). We use this questionnaire regularly (along with others) with our students of Psychology, in trials and for research, and obtain participants with high scores, whose mental health we do not question. Healthy people often show poorly-defined boundaries between imagination and reality without this dragging a diagnosis of schizophrenia or mental illness, in the same way that major and sub-clinical depression exists (Fonseca-Pedrero, et al., 2011). In this sense, perhaps we can find a continuum or a mental line between schizotypy and schizophrenia in relation to these cognitive biases: lower biases magnitude in low schizotypy versus high schizotypy healthy participants and higher biases magnitude in people with schizophrenia versus people scoring high on a schizotypy scale.

As we claimed, to achieve our goals, we used a new version of Drawing to Decision Task (DDT). In this new version, we have introduced new parameters as the Feedback Sensitivity and a number of correct answers, in order to clarify why JTC bias happens. The analysis of the Feedback Sensitivity will allow us to find out if this cognitive bias is only present when subjects have been instructed to derive their own interpretations or when more sources of information are available and the decision-making context has been previously defined. This last characteristic allows us to analyse the effect of the context in which the decisions are taken. The analysis of accuracy let us know whether JTC is related or not to efficacy. Like in the previous versions of the tasks, the principal dependent measure was the plausibility rating of each stimulus presented at all stages and the number of stimulus necessary to reach a final

decision about their identity. We also computed BADE (Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence) in DDT following Moritz and Woodward (2006).

In short, we have chained the following hypotheses: 1. JTC is a clinical judgment that could be useful to predict first episodes of psychosis: We expect higher JTC bias in patients with schizophrenia followed by persons with high schizotypy and the lowest (or null) JTC bias in participants with low schizotypy 2. JTC is related negatively with accuracy but only in the difficult version of the task (uncued trials). 3. JTC is related to Feedback Sensitivity (FS) but only in the difficult version of the task (uncued trials). 4. JTC is related to BADE (we expect a high correlation between BADE and FS specially). 5. Our previous hypotheses maintain that the more JTC the less Feedback Sensitivity and accuracy. Following this line of thinking, patients with schizophrenia show higher JTC (and BADE) and are less sensitive to feedback and therefore have more difficulty changing their misinterpretation than high schizotypy subjects (lower accuracy). A similar pattern would happen for high schizotypy participants with respect to low schizotypy ones.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

A total of 45 people participated in this experiment. We used a group of 15 patients with schizophrenia, and two control groups with high (n=15) and low schizotypy (n=15). The inclusion criteria for the patients with schizophrenia were: having a diagnosis of functional psychosis according to the DSM-IV-TR (295-297-298, and 296 with psychotic codes) (APA, 1994). The presence and intensity of psychotic symptoms was assessed by means of the PANSS scale (Kay et al., 1987). The PANSS has been validated on a Spanish population of patients with schizophrenia (Peralta &

Cuesta, 1994). With respect to healthy participants, 169 undergraduate students were assessed to baseline vulnerability to psychosis with the Community Assessment of Psychic Experience, CAPE (Konings et al., 2006). The inclusion criteria for the control subjects with high schizotypy got a total score higher than 1.6 but inside the range for normal population (because the score for non-clinical populations were found to range from 1.4 to 1.8). The inclusion criteria for the control subjects with low schizotypy got a total score lower than 1.5 but inside the range for normal population. Out of the 88 subjects contacted, 42 agreed to participate. The final sample consisted in 15 high schizotypy and 15 low schizotypy individuals, as data were lost for several participants due to technical difficulties or missing values. BADE task data from five schizotypal subjects were lost because of computer crashes. Seven participants were excluded due to incomplete questionnaires. Premorbid intelligence was determined by Test de acentuación de palabras TAP-30 (González Montalvo, 1991). All participants reported an absence of cerebral damage and no clinical evidence of drug abuse during the course of the study. Also, healthy participants reported an absence of mental disorder. See Table 1.

2.2. Procedure

Participants were tested individually in two experimental sessions; each one lasted approximately 60 minutes. Testing was conducted in a distraction-free quiet room. In the first sessions all participants were conducted with questionnaires. In the second sessions everything was screened with the Pictures Decision Task.

Community Assessment of Psychic Experience, CAPE

For two control groups, baseline vulnerability to psychosis was assessed with the Community Assessment of Psychic Experience, CAPE (Konings et al., 2006). This scale evaluates three basic dimensions (negative, positive and the depressive symptoms) of psychotic spectrum to assess order psychotic experiences and psychotic symptoms in the general population. The positive scale, of 18 items, comprises delusions, hallucinations, suspiciousness/ideas of persecution, unusual thought content. The 14 items of the negative scale cover flat affect, emotional withdrawal, lack of relationship, passive social withdrawal, and lack of spontaneity. The 8 items of the depressive scale included cognitive symptoms of the depression such as sadness, pessimism, hopelessness, feeling a failure or feeling guilty. The CAPE has correct psychometric behavior regarding internal consistency, temporal stability and different evidences of validity (Stefanis et al., 2002; Hanssen et al., 2003), so it would be used as a screening instrument in the general population. The CAPE has been adapted and validated on Spanish healthy population (Fonseca-Pedrero, Paino, Lemos-Giráldez, & Muñiz, 2012; Ros-Morente, Vilagra-Ruiz, Rodriguez-Hansen, Wigman, & Barrantes-Vidal, 2011).

The TAP-30 is a measure of intelligence in which the participant is instructed to read 30 words of irregular pronunciation. It is a Spanish adaptation validated through the North American Adult Reading Test (NART; Nelson, 1982). The NART was developed as a measure for estimating premorbid intelligence in patients with schizophrenia (for a review, see O'Carroll, 1995; Russell et al., 2000) and is believed to prove a good estimate of premorbid IQ because it: (a) predicts much of the variance in current WAIS IQ; (b) has high reliability in normal subjects (Kondel et al., 2003).

The Pictures Decision Task

Our experimental procedure is a version of the picture task created by Moritz & Woodward (2007). Ten experimental trials, following two practice trials, were presented. Each trial consisted in a sequence of eight stages, each showing a common object that was increasingly disambiguated by decreasing degrees of visual fragmentation: new object features were added to each new picture until, eventually, the entire object was displayed in the final stage. The objects were depicted as post-edit simple black and white drawings. Instructions and trials were presented using a computer. There were two types of trials (cued and “uncued”). In the cued trials, the drawings were accompanied by a list of six possible interpretations (cues) and the participants were asked to choose an answer and assess the plausibility of their choice on a 5-point Likert scale. In the uncued trials no interpretative cues were provided and the participants were instructed to derive their own interpretations. The practice trials are a guitar with cue and a raft without cue. The experimental trials were run in a fixed order and fully counterbalanced. In all these trials their plausibility was then rated using a five-point Likert scale (1= dismissed, 2= unlikely, 3= possible, 4= likely, 5= positive decision). Examples of the task can be seen in Appendices 4 (cued trial) and 5 (uncued trial). During this new version of this task, the presentation of the stages was not interrupted until the participants finish up the drawing, even when the participants evaluate their decision with maximum security before the last stage. We also conceptually divided the task into two parts (the first part consisting of four stages and the last consisting of four stages). In the first four stages, in the pictures formal elements of the drawing predominated (circles, lines, etc...) and so the subject could only develop interpretative hypothesis. Throughout the last four stages the pictures started to be outlined, and the addition of new elements acted as a feedback on the previous response.

In this new version of the task, different new parameters can be calculated and then used to provide further insight into the underlying mechanisms of JTC bias. Specifically, five parameters were calculated (three old ones and two new ones): Plausibility Rating (PR), BADE and Draws To Decision (DTD) as the old ones, Number of correct answers (Ac) and Feedback Sensitivity (FS) as the new ones.

The Plausibility Rating (PR) was defined as the means to plausibility rating at the eight stages for cued and uncued trials (range 1 to 5). This parameters is used to measure the level of conviction that the subject expresses for his interpretations of the drawing

The Draws To Decision (DTD) was defined as the means to number of stages for cued and uncued trials necessary for the participant to reach a final decision about the identity of the objects with absolute certainty (range 1 to 8; the total number of stages per trial).

The Number of correct responses or accuracy (Acc) at the last stage (stage 8) (max: 5 for cued and 5 for uncued trials).

The Feedback Sensitivity (FS) relates the number of error vs. the number of wrong guesses accomplished in the last four stages. This index checks whether the person realizes it he was wrong and tries to change the interpretation of the drawing using the new information received (at each stage) or if he is anchored to the previous wrong answer. To calculate this index we add to the number of errors (E, taking into account the repetitions) the inverse of the number of wrong guesses (C=number of different wrong conjectures). $FS = (\sum E + 1/\sum C)$. In this index, a low score means that the feedback is more used.

Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE) is the difference score between mean plausibility ratings for incorrect interpretations at the first stage relative to the

mean plausibility ratings for incorrect interpretations at later stages. The signature of a BADE effect would be a lower reduction of plausibility ratings for incorrect interpretations across stages (Moritz and Woodward, 2006). Simple mean comparisons were used to determine group differences for the BADE parameter at the different stages. Apart from this main parameter (difference score initial vs. later rating for incorrect responses), we also assessed the horizontal stability of our results to detect if they showed any evident trend, with the C statistic (Young, 1941, Suen and Ary, 1989).

3.Results

3.1. Socio-demographic variables

The samples did not differ on any major socio-demographic background variables (age, gender, formal school education, intelligence). Post-hoc group comparisons were more significant $P=0.1$ for all parameters, even before correction for multiple comparisons (See Table 1).

3.2. Drawing to Decision Task

Statistical analyses were carried out with SPSS Version 17.0. On the Pictures Decision Task we conducted separate analysis of variance on the different dependent variables. For all analyses, the scores were compared among the three groups (patients with schizophrenia and two control groups-high and low schizotypy). On the Plausibility Rating an ANOVA was performed with a between factor (Group: patients with schizophrenia vs. control groups) and two within factors: condition (with cue vs. without cue), stage (1 to 8th stage). For the other parameters (Draws to Decision, Accuracy, Feedback Sensitivity) separate ANOVAs were calculated with a between factor (patients with schizophrenia vs. control groups) and a within factor (condition

with cue vs. without cue). The analyses about BADE were performed as ratings from cued and uncued trials collapsed. All results are reported as between-groups t-tests for five BADE measures (at stages 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) like in Moritz and Woodward (2006) figure 1 and with the C statistic. Finally, correlational analyses were conducted on the entire sample between the indices of the Pictures Decision Task.

3.2.1 Plausibility rating

There was a significant main effect of cue, [$F(1, 42) = 121.751, p < 0.001$]: the participants were more confident about their interpretations in the cued condition with respect to the uncued condition (3.34 vs. 2.55). There was also a significant cue x group interaction, [$F(2, 42) = 7.164, p < 0.05$]. All groups expressed greater certainty of judgment in the cued condition. See Figure 1. The difference in PR between cued and uncued conditions was significant for all groups. For patients, (Mean=2.662 SD= 0.137, Mean=3.094 SD=0.131, $p=.001$). For the control groups, the difference between cued and uncued trials in PR was also significant (Mean=2.636 SD= 0.137, Mean=3.725 SD=0.131, $p=.000$) and (Mean=2.351 SD= 0.137, Mean=3.205 SD=0.131, $p=.000$), respectively for high and low schizotypy participants. The only significant difference between patients with schizophrenia and control groups (high schizotypy and low schizotypy) in PR occurred in the cued condition, [$F(2, 42) = 6.594, p < 0.05$] and [$F(2, 42) = 4.502, p < 0.06$] for the comparison between patients with high and low schizotypy participants respectively, being controls participants more confident than patients with schizophrenia.

Figure 1. Cue x Group interaction between patients with schizophrenia, and the other two healthy groups (high and low schizotypy) in the cued and uncued condition.

The stage effect was significant [$F(7, 294) = 174.138, p < 0.001$]: the certainty increased significantly at all stages (1.98, 2.18, 2.36, 2.59, 2.90, 3.21, 3.81, 4.50). Also the cue x stage interaction was significant [$F(7, 294) = 11.901, p < 0.001$]. Participants expressed greater confidence in the cued condition with respect to the condition without cue at all stages. In the cued condition at stages 1, 2, the certainty differed significantly from PR in the stage 3. From the stages 3 to 8, the certainty increased significantly at each stage. But in the uncued condition, at stages 1 to 4 we found a similar PR. The certainty grows slightly but significantly from the stages 4 to 6. By stages 6 to 8 the certainty continued growing significantly again but with higher slope. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. Plausibility Rating in the two conditions (cued trials and uncued trials). Vertical axis reflects the range of this parameter (1-5, the five points of plausibility rating). Horizontal axis reflects the number of stages. ^{“a”} significant difference between cued and uncued trials for each stage (from stage 1 to 8), $p = .0001$.

There was also a significant stage x group interaction [$F(14, 294) = 4.657, p < 0.001$]. There were significant differences between patients with schizophrenia vs. low schizotypy participants at stages 1 [$F(2, 42) = 7.579, p < 0.05$], 2 [$F(2, 42) = 6.722, p < 0.05$] and stage 8, [$F(2, 42) = 6.955, p < 0.05$], where patients with schizophrenia showed more self-confidence. We also obtained significant differences between high schizotypy participants and patients at stages 1 [$F(2, 42) = 8.055, p < 0.05$], 6 [$F(2, 42)$

= 6.722, $p < 0.05$], 7 [$F(2, 42) = 7.936$, $p < 0.05$] and stage 8 [$F(2, 42) = 9.637$, $p < 0.05$]. Patients with schizophrenia showed more certainty in their hypothesis at the first stage when there is less information but they showed less confidence at the last stages when there is more information. The controls participants showed more security in their hypothesis at the last stages when there is more information on disposal and less certainty at the first stages when there is less information available. No other group differences were significant, $F < 1$. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Plausibility Rating for the three groups (stage x group interaction).

Vertical axis reflects the range of this parameter (1-5, the five points of plausibility rating). Horizontal axis reflects the number of stages.

3.2.2 Draws to Decisions (DTD)

There was a significant main effect of cue [$F(1, 42) = 11.557$, $p < 0.05$], (5.93 vs. 6.66) with quicker responses in the cued condition. There was also a significant cue x group interaction [$F(2, 42) = 7.65$, $p < 0.05$]. In fact, high and low schizotypy groups (6.74 and 7.37) showed higher DTD scores in the uncued trials than patients with schizophrenia (5.89). Only high schizotypy groups showed differences significant between cued and uncued condition (Mean=5.300 SD=0.361 Mean= 6.743 SD= 0.334 $p = .001$). Two independent t-test samples were run to comparing means between groups. There were significant differences between low schizotypy group and patients with schizophrenia in the uncued condition. The patients with schizophrenia showed more absolute security before than low schizotypy participants (Mean=5.891 SD=1.984 Mean= 7.373 SD= 0.736 $p = .003$). We also found almost significant differences in DTD

between high schizotypy participants and patients with schizophrenia. The patients with schizophrenia showed clearer and more absolute security before than high schizotypy individuals (Mean=5.891 SD=1.984 Mean= 6.742 SD= 0.807 $p=.006$). The DTD differences between groups for the cued trials were non-significant (6.1, 5.8 and 6.3 respectively).

3.2.3 Number of correct answers at Stage 8.

There was a significant main effect of cue [$F(1, 42) = 27.421, p < 0.001$]. The participants showed higher scores in the cued condition (4.55 vs. 3.82). That means that the uncued condition is a more difficult version of the task. There were not other significant effects of group or significant interactions.

3.2.4 Feedback sensitivity

There was a significant main effect of cue [$F(1, 42) = 200.39, p < 0.001$]: In the cued condition feedback was more used than in the uncued condition (5.82 vs. 11.60). There was a significant main effect of group [$F(2, 42) = 6.459, p < 0.05$]: the controls were more sensitive to the feedback than the patients with schizophrenia (8.12, 8.32 and 9.69 for high schizotypy participants, low schizotypy participants and patients with schizophrenia respectively). There was not a significant group x cue interaction.

3.2.5. Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE)

The analyses about BADE was made with collapsed ratings from cued and uncued trials, as Trial Type (cued, uncued) did not yield any significant interaction with Group (patients with schizophrenia, high schizotypy, low schizotypy) when entered as an additional within-subject factor. See Figure 4 with Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE): change scores (initial stage to subsequent stages) averaged over

uncued and cued trials. Patients with schizophrenia decreased their plausibility scores significantly less than controls across time: -0.45 versus -1.0 respectively, being the decrement significant only for controls but not for patients ($C=0.57$, $p=0.03$; $C=0.46$, $P=0.04$ and $C=0.22$, $p=0.20$, respectively). For absolute plausibility scores, group differences no yielded significance.

Figure 4. Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE) — change Scores in stages 2 to 6, following Moritz and Woodward (2006), figure 1.

3.2.6. Correlational analyses.

The correlations show that [see tables 2 to 9 in Appendix 1 (JTC bias), appendix 2 (BADE) and appendix 3 (three dimensions' squizotypy with JTC/BADE bias)]:

-There negative associations between PR and DTD in the first part of stages (stage 2) for patients with schizophrenia. That is to say that when a strong conviction exists at the beginning of the decision making process, fewer stages are necessary to arrive at a final decision: so JTC. However, in the group of low schizotypy participants, it is appreciated more negative associations between PR and DTD in the last stages.

There are negative correlations between accuracy and PR1, so accuracy is related to JTC in patients with schizophrenia. Also there are positive correlations between accuracy and PR7 in low schizotypy, so this does reinforce more our hypothesis about this relationship between accuracy and JTC. Only the control groups showed positive correlations between PR and accuracy at last stages

(what suggest more accuracy with better confidence for these stages or vice versa)

Finally, there is a negative correlation between accuracy and Feedback sensitivity in the groups of high schizotypy and patients with schizophrenia.. The reader can remember now that the control group made better use of feedback and showed more plausibility, less DTD than in the uncued condition and better accuracy in the final stages.

In more specific correlations, it is observed that there were strong positive associations between the positive dimension of schizotypy and PR, and negative with DTD and the other way around, there were negative correlations between negative dimension of schizotypy with PR in high schizotypy group, like we were expected it. Low schizotypy groups display negative correlations between DTD and positive in the last stage in the positive dimension only

-There are negative significant correlations between BADE and PR for all groups (except for high schizotypy participants in PR at stage 1). BADE is not related to accuracy or FS for patients and high schizotypy participants. In the case of low schizotypy participants, we found negative correlations with accuracy and FS (the bias is related with feedback use and less accuracy) but only for last stages. For the control groups (high and low schizotypy participants, overall for low ones), there is a positive correlation between BADE and DTD. Also, BADE had negative correlations with the positive dimensions only in high schizotypy individuals. For patients, the correlation between BADE and DTD is negative at early stages and positive for last stages.

4.Discussion

The present results evidence that a Jumping to Conclusions bias may be related to propensity to hold strong beliefs (high PR at first stages) and/or to low feedback sensitivity (FS). Previous studies have examined the relationship between JTC bias, schizophrenia and schizotypy (Speechley et al., 2010; Rodier et al., 2011). However, our contribution is to add new parameters and analyze the relationship between BADE and JTC bias with these new parameters. Especially we analysed like FS may be key in the difference cognitive between schizophrenia and schizotypy. FS could be a second factor related to JTC. We found similar JTC in the cued condition for all groups (two control groups and patients) but earlier JTC in the uncued condition for patients and high schizotypy participants and higher JTC bias in the uncued condition for patients (more PR at early stages, less DTD than controls) related to less accuracy and less feedback use.

In the cued condition, patients benefit less from cues, showed similar DTD than in the uncued condition, less confidence at last stages and less use of the feedback but similar accuracy. What could mean that feedback sensitivity is independent of JTC bias in this context (easy version of the task with more sources of information available and the context of the decision previously defined). FS is unrelated to DTD and related to PR only in the last stages in the cued condition but only for the controls. The control groups made better use of feedback and showed more plausibility, less DTD than in the uncued condition and better accuracy in the last stages in the cued condition.

The pattern of results is different for the uncued trials or difficult version of the task (with less accuracy). For the uncued condition, we found also than the patients showed more confidence at first stage and less confidence at last stages but the control groups showed the opposite pattern. At the same time, the patients showed less DTD or quicker decisions. That is we found more JTC bias for patients in the uncued condition

even if the negative correlation between PR and DTD was significant for both groups (patients and high schizotypy participants) at first stage. The patients showed also in the uncued condition less feedback sensitivity. An open question is whether JTC (higher PR at first stage and less DTD) is related to less use of the feedback in the uncued condition for patients. The high schizotypy participants behaved like low schizotypy participants in the cued condition (better confidence, feedback use and accuracy in last stages) but like patients with schizophrenia in the uncued condition (JTC bias at first stage, less feedback use and worse accuracy with more confidence in early stages). High schizotypy participants showed an opposite pattern of relationships between FS, Acc and PR in the cued and uncued conditions. Overall, high PR at first stages were related negatively with accuracy and positively with FS (less use of feedback) in the uncued condition. For the cued condition, high PR at last stages were related negatively with FS (better use of feedback) and positively with accuracy. This difference could be considered in favor of a relationship between JTC and FS overall in the uncued condition. BADE is not related to accuracy or feedback use. Even more, BADE is related to lower PR and higher DTD, what implies that BADE is unrelated to JTC bias characterized by high PR and low DTD.

Our results also demonstrate that in general the patients with schizophrenia were less sensitive to the feedback compared to the control groups. The patients with schizophrenia were more reluctant to change a belief when new evidence does not confirm it. They were less able to integrate disconfirming evidence. Although, the cue serves as a facilitator in the feedback use, as can be observed in the control group who make quicker decisions in the cued condition. The patients have not benefited when there were interpretative aids. More important JTC (in the cued condition) is not related to accuracy. What means that JTC could be a good heuristic tool under certain

conditions or that our task is too easy to show a relationship between accuracy and JTC. However, in the uncued condition, the negative correlations between PR at first stages and accuracy and the positive correlations between DTD and accuracy can be considered in favour of a negative relationship between JTC bias and accuracy for difficult versions of the task. In general, accuracy is negatively correlated with feedback sensitivity. In conclusion, JTC is a general bias also presented in non-clinical population but it happens earlier and with higher magnitude in clinical population. This bias is not related to feedback use in the cued condition but it could be related to a general bias against use of feedback in the uncued condition. We need more research to solve the incongruent results between cued and uncued conditions (context effect).

The result found in the present study should be interpreted considering the following limitations. First, there is the problem inherent to the application any type of self-report. Second, to assess the representativeness of the sample, it would have been favorable to determine additional cognitive (e.g., executive functioning, reasoning) and meta-cognitive measures. Third, the present sample was a small one. Thus, group differences may have failed to emerge due to a lack of power.

About future directions, the present findings offer potential therapeutic implications. If delusion formation and maintenance are mediated via a general JTC bias and low feedback use, cognitive therapy in schizophrenia could use tasks such as the ones employed in the present study to promote more efficient hypothesis testing through better feedback use.

References

- American Psychiatric Association, 2000. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth ed. rev. (DSM-IV-TR). American Psychiatric Association, Washington, DC.
- Balzan, R., Delfabbro, P., Galletly, C. & Woodward, T. S., 2012. Reasoning Heuristics across the Psychosis Continuum: The Contribution of Hypersalient Evidence-hypothesis Matches. *Cognitive Neuropsychiatry*. DOI:10.1080/13546805.2012.663901.
- Broome M.R., Johns L.C., Valli I., Woolley J.B., Tabraham P., Brett C., Valmaggia L., Peters E., Garety P.A., McGuire P.K., 2007. Delusion formation and reasoning biases in those at clinical high risk for psychosis. *British Journal of Psychiatry*. Supplement 51 38-42.
- Buchy, L., Woodward, T.S., Liotti, M., 2007. A cognitive bias against disconfirmatory evidence (BADE) is associated with schizotypy. *Schizophrenia Research*, 90, 334-337.
- Claridge, G.S. & Beech, T., 1995. Fully and quasi-dimensional constructions of schizotypy. In: Raine, A., Lencz, T., Mednick, S.A. (Eds), *Schizotypal Personality*. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- First M.B., Spitzer R.L., Gibbon M., Williams J.B.W., 1997. *Structured Clinical Interview for DSMIV Axis I Disorders (Clinician version)*. First edition. American Psychiatric Association, Washington, DC.
- Fonseca-Pedrero E., Paino M., Lemos-Giráldez S., Muñiz J., 2011. Schizotypal traits and depressive symptoms in nonclinical adolescents. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 52 (3), 293-300.

Fonseca-Pedrero, E., Paino, M., Lemos-Giráldez, S., & Muñiz, J., 2012. Validation of the Community Assessment Psychic Experiences -42 (CAPE-42) in Spanish college students and patients with psychosis. *Actas Españolas de Psiquiatría*, 40, 169-176.

Freeman D., Pugh K., Garety P., 2008. Jumping to conclusions and paranoid ideation in the general population. *Schizophrenia Research*, 102, 254–260.

González Montalvo, J.A., 1991. Creación y validación de un test de lectura para el diagnóstico del deterioro mental en el anciano. Tesis Doctoral. Universidad Complutense, Madrid.

Hanssen, M., Peeters, F., Krabbendam, L., Radstake, S., Verdoux, H., y van Os, J., 2003. How psychotic are individuals with non-psychotic disorders? *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 38(3), 149-154.

Huq S.F., Garety P.A., Hemsley D.R., 1988. Probabilistic judgements in deluded and non-deluded subjects. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 40 (4) 801-12.

Johns, L. C., y van Os, J., 2001. The continuity psychotic experiences in the general population *Clinical Psychology Review*, 21, 1125-1141.

Kay S.R., Fiszbein A., Opler L.A., 1987. The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) for Schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 23 (1) 99-110.

Kondel, T. K., Mortimer, A. M., Verity, C. L., Laws, K. R., & Hirsch, S. R., 2003. Intellectual differences between schizophrenic patients and normal controls across the adult lifespan. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology*, 25, 1045-1056.

Konings M., Back M., Hansen M., van Os J., Krabbendam L., 2006. Validity and reliability of the CAPE: a self-report instrument for the measurement of psychotic experiences in the general population. *Acta Psychiatrica Scand*, 114(1) 55-61.

Kwapil, T. R., Barrantes Vidal, N., & Silvia, P. J., 2008. The dimensional structure of the Wisconsin schizotypy scales: Factor identification and construct validity. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 34, 444-457.

Lenzenweger M. F., 2010. Current status of the scientific study of the personality disorders: Epidemiologic, longitudinal, experimental psychopathology, and neurobehavioral perspectives (*Distinguished Invited Essay*). *Journal of the American Psychoanalytic Association*, 58: 741-778.

Levitan L., & LaBerge S., 1991. Other worlds: out-of-body experiences and lucid dreams. *Nightlight*, 3(2): 1-5.

Lincoln T.M., Ziegler M., Mehl S., Rief W., 2011. The jumping to conclusions bias in delusions: specificity and changeability. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 119 (1) 40-9.

Moritz S., Woodward T.S., 2005. Jumping to conclusions in delusional and non-delusional schizophrenic patients. *The British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 44 (Pt2) 193-207.

Moritz S., Woodward T.S., Lambert M., 2007. Under what circumstances do patients with schizophrenia jump to conclusions? A liberal acceptance account. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 46(Pt 2):127-37.

Moritz S., Woodward T.S., 2006. A generalized bias against disconfirmatory evidence in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research*, 142 (2-3) 157-65.

Munz, M. T., 2011. *Jumping to Conclusions, Liberal Acceptance and the Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence: An Evaluation of Reasoning Deviations in Delusions*. Rostock University. urn:nbn:de:gbv:28-diss2012-0089-5.

Nelson, H.E, 1982. *The National Adult Reading Test (NART): Test Manual*. Windsor: NFER-Nelson.

O'Carroll, R. (1995). The assessment of premorbid ability: A critical review. *Neurocase*, 1, 83–89.

Peralta V., Cuesta M.J., 1994. Psychometric properties of the positive and negative syndrome scale (PANSS) in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research*, 53 (1) 31-40.

Raine, A., 2006b. Schizotypal personality: neurodevelopmental and psychosocial trajectories. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 2, 291– 326.

Rodier M., Prévost M., Renoult L., Lionnet C., Kwann Y., Dionne-Dostie E., Chapleau I., Debruille J.B., 2011. Healthy people with delusional ideation change their mind with conviction. *Psychiatry Research*, 189, 433–439.

Ros-Morente, A., Vilagra-Ruiz, R., Rodriguez-Hansen, G., Wigman, J. H., & Barrantes-Vidal, N., 2011. Process of adaptation to Spanish of the Community Assessment of Psychic Experiences (CAPE). *Actas Españolas de Psiquiatría*, 39, 95-105.

Rubio J.L., Ruíz- Veguilla M., Hernández L., Barrigón M.L., Salcedo M.D., Moreno J.M., Gómez E., Moritz S., Ferrín M., 2011. Jumping to conclusions in psychosis: a faulty appraisal. *Shizophrenia Research*, 133 (1-3) 199-204.

Russell, A.J., Munro, J.C., Jones, P.B., Hayward, P., Hemsley, D.R., & Murray, R.M., 2000. The National Adult Reading Test as a measure of premorbid IQ in schizophrenia. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 39, 297–305.

Speechley W.J., Whitman J.C., Woodward T.S., 2010. The contribution of hypersalience to the "jumping to conclusions" bias associated with delusions in schizophrenia. *Journal of Psychiatry & Neuroscience*. 35 (1) 7-17.

Stefanis N. C., Hanssen M., Smirnis N K., Avramopoulos D. A., Evdokimidis I. K., Stefanis C. N., Verdoux H., Van Os J., 2002. Evidence that three dimensions of psychosis have a distribution in the general population. *Psychological Medicine*, 32(2), 347-358.

Suen, H.K. & Ary, D., 1989. Analyzing quantitative behavioral observation data. Hillsdale, NJ.: LEA.

Van Dael F., Versmissen D., Janssen I., Myin-Germeys I., van Os J., Krabbendam L., 2006. Data gathering: biased in psychosis?. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 32 (2) 341-51.

Van Os, J., Hanssen, M., Bijl, R. V., & Ravelli, A., 2000. Strauss (1969) revisited: a psychosis continuum in the general population? *Schizophrenia Research*, 45, 11– 20.

Van Os, J., Kenis G., & Rutten B. PF., 2010. The environment and schizophrenia. *Nature*, 468, 203-212.

Verdoux, H., y Van Os, J., 2002. Psychotic symptoms in non-clinical populations and the continuum of psychosis. *Schizophrenia Research*, 54, 59-65.

Warman, D.M., Lysaker, P.H., & Martin, J.M., 2007. Cognitive insight and psychotic disorders: The impact of active delusion. *Schizophrenia Research*, 90, 325-333.

Young, L.C., 1941. On randomness in ordered sequences. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 12, 293-300.

Table 1. Sociodemographic and psychopathological variables

Variable	Shizophrenia(n=15)	High (n=15)	schizotypy Low (n=15)	schizotypy	Statistics; LSD post-hoc
<i>Sociodemographic variables</i>					
Age	39.20 (6.179)	31.53 (2.356)	32.27 (5.311)		$F(2,37)=4.246$ $p=.022$ NS
Gender	7M, 8F	6 M, 9 F	5 M, 10 F		$\chi^2(2)=0.556$ $p=.757$ NS
Years of formal education	13.60(1.765)	13.40(1.454)	13.67(1.234)		$F(2,42)=0.128$ $p=.088$ NS
Premorbid intelligence (IQ)	15.80 (2.512)	16.33 (2.257)	16.20 (2.980)		$F(2,42)=0.717$ $p=.844$ NS
<i>Psychopathological variables</i>					
PANSS total score	66.80 (8.402)	–	–		

Appendix 1.

Table 2. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task in the cued condition conduct on all groups.

	JTC (Cued Trial)								
	Schizophrenia			High schizotypy			Low schizotypy		
	DTD	Acc	FS	DTD	Acc	FS	DTD	Acc	FS
PR1	.029	-.078	.127	-.062	.117	-.101	-.014	.342	.129
PR2	-.451*	-.131	.201	-.561*	.037	.049	-.343	.545*	.112
PR3	-.424	.041	-.041	-.012	.261	-.210	-.320	.046	.169
PR4	-.536*	-.081	.102	-.150	.233	-.190	-.569*	.066	.425
PR5	-.610*	-.284	.084	-.192	.425	-.281	-.537*	.117	.553*
PR6	-.432	.081	.123	-.470*	.325	-.162	-.597*	.218	.300
PR7	-.378	.035	-.024	-.417	.647**	-.477*	-.600*	.180	-.146
PR8	.193	.131	-.365	-.066	.422	-.455*	-.503	.446	-.100
DTD	1	.244	.041	1	-.176	.027	1	-.252	-.006
ACC	.244	1	-.382	-.176	1	-.86**	-.252	1	-.030
FS	.029	-.382	1	.027	-.86**	1	-.006	-.030	1

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Table 3. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task in the uncued condition conduct on all groups.

JTC (Uncued Trial)									
	Schizophrenia			High schizotypy			Low schizotypy		
	DTD	Acc	FS	DTD	Acc	FS	DTD	Acc	FS
PR1	-.365*	-.535*	.434*	-.477*	-.337*	.631**	,272	,276	-,238
PR2	-.409*	-.490*	.439*	-.161	-.357*	.330*	-,466	,184	-,132
PR3	-.187	-.666**	.486*	-.361	-.454*	,295	-.542*	,260	-,183
PR4	-.258	-.583*	.523*	-.343	-.520*	,296	-,377	,178	-,232
PR5	-.414	,409	,172	-.215	-.182	,016	-,424	,243	-,195
PR6	-.184	-.481*	,321	-.149	,101	-.156	-,448	,505	-,388
PR7	,222	,177	-.102	-.185	,097	-.295	-,369	.666**	-,378
PR8	.750**	.486*	-.386	-.120	,250	-.418	-,209	.648*	-,488
DTD	1	,491	-.078	1	.484*	-.457	1	-,092	-,097
ACC	,491	1	-.750**	.484*	1	-.782*	-,092	1	-.852**
FS	-.078	-.750**	1	-.457	-.782*	1	-,097	-.852**	1

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Appendix 2.

Table 4. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task and BADE (collapsing the uncued and cued conditions) conduct on patients with schizophrenia.

Schizophrenia							
BADE							
Change	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PR1	,011	,164	,238	,167	,174	,313	,322
PR2	-,737**	-,349	-,493*	-,456*	-,196	,172	,326
PR3	-,551*	-,526*	-,393	-,274	-,146	,138	,064
PR4	-,686**	-,502*	-,618**	-,648**	-,511*	-,194	,010
PR5	-,671**	-,395	-,590*	-,792**	-,608**	-,250	,080
PR6	-,363	-,487*	-,504*	-,711**	-,774**	-,543*	-,297
DTD	,499*	-,098	,248	,415	,057	-,288	-,568*
Acc	,119	-,137	-,009	-,050	-,117	-,310	-,388
FS	,056	-,160	-,013	,128	-,017	,216	,011

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Table 5. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task and BADE (collapsing the uncued and cue conditions) conduct on high schizotypy.

High schizotypy							
BADE							
Change	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PR1	,181	,212	,172	,465*	,658**	,644**	,539*
PR2	-,571*	-,148	-,522*	-,178	,090	,061	,204
PR3	-,420	-,839**	-,359	-,125	,120	,033	-,157
PR4	-,466*	-,283	-,614**	-,318	-,061	-,110	-,012
PR5	-,340	-,199	-,501*	-,418	-,181	-,203	-,060
PR6	-,433	,025	-,466*	-,632**	-,587*	-,459*	-,211
DTD	,266	,201	,571*	,244	,268	,373	,097
Acc	,111	,165	,174	-,095	-,315	-,313	,056
FS	,175	,120	,093	,213	,397	,457*	,096

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Table 6. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task and BADE (collapsing the uncued and cue conditions) conduct on low schizotypy.

Low schizotypy							
Change	BADE						
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PR1	-,148	-,085	,025	,009	-,172	,084	-,133
PR2	-,744**	-,657**	-,478*	-,555*	-,684**	,097	-,268
PR3	-,765**	-,776**	-,511*	-,575*	-,733**	,126	-,255
PR4	-,643**	-,655**	-,781**	-,649**	-,636**	-,256	-,692**
PR5	-,774**	-,705**	-,764**	-,759**	-,838**	-,311	-,672**
PR8	-,354	-,498*	-,197	-,310	-,360	-,300	-,647**
DTD	,706**	,746**	,395	,497*	,597**	-,052	,485*
Acc	-,280	-,277	-,259	-,356	-,291	-,155	-,565*
FS	,135	,173	-,219	-,179	-,234	-,491*	-,163

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Appendix 3.

Table 7. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task with three dimensions (positive, negative and depressive) of schizotypy conduct on high schizotypy.

	High Schizotypy					
	Uncued Trials			Cued Trials		
	Positive	Negative	Depressive	Positive	Negative	Depressive
PR1	,064	-,268	,371	,069	-,317	,444*
PR2	,320	-,594**	-,260	,530*	-,596**	,089
PR3	,521*	-,414	-,202	-,111	-,032	,058
PR4	,547*	-,408	-,041	,254	-,144	,508*
PR5	,547*	-,282	-,317	,232	-,174	,569*
PR6	,503*	-,301	-,493*	,466*	-,292	,243
PR7	,510*	-,315	-,527*	,543*	-,165	,165
PR8	-,040	,247	-,338	,292	-,091	-,069
DTD	-,426	,154	-,378	-,695**	,618**	-,158
ACC	-,184	,293	-,384	,432	,080	,008
FS	,076	-,270	,499*	-,302	-,075	,256

Table 8. Results of Pearson's correlation between the parameters of the Picture Decision Task with three dimensions (positive, negative and depressive) of schizotypy conduct on low schizotypy.

Low Schizotypy						
	Uncued Trials			Cued Trials		
	Positive	Negative	Depressive	Positive	Negative	Depressive
PR1	,423	,260	-,111	,406	,409	,067
PR2	,367	,139	-,072	,341	,160	,268
PR3	,385	,096	-,005	,438	,349	,408
PR4	,113	-,115	,170	,425	,202	,269
PR5	,258	,089	,125	,437	,166	,307
PR6	,513*	,156	-,187	,575*	,307	,138
PR7	,583*	,338	-,009	,126	-,167	-,138
PR8	,498*	,247	-,074	,392	,056	-,304
DTD	-,383	-,019	,359	-,630**	-,168	,116
ACC	,373	,258	,074	,289	,122	-,174
FS	-,428	-,155	,030	,072	,126	,427

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Table 9. Results of Pearson's correlation between BADE (collapsing the uncued and cue conditions) with three dimensions (positive, negative and depressive) of schizotypy conduct on high/low schizotypy.

Dimension	JTC (Cued Trial)					
	High schizotypy			Low schizotypy		
	Positive	Negative	Depressive	Positive	Negative	Depressive
BADE2	-,485*	,231	,405	-,255	,013	-,057
BADE3	-,061	-,059	,136	-,349	-,140	-,159
BADE4	-,641**	,342	,114	-,014	,101	-,432
BADE5	-,465*	,084	,402	-,162	-,025	-,318
BADE6	-,365	-,009	,448*	-,357	-,143	-,308

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$

Figure 1. Cue x Group interaction between patients with schizophrenia, and the other two healthy groups (high and low schizotypy) in the cued and uncued condition.

Figure 2. Plausibility Rating in the two conditions (cued trials and uncued trials). Vertical axis reflects the range of this parameter (1-5, the five points of plausibility rating). Horizontal axis reflects the number of stages. "a" significant difference between cued and uncued trials for each stage (from stage 1 to 8), $p=.0001$.

Figure 3. Plausibility Rating for the three groups (stage x group interaction).

Vertical axis reflects the range of this parameter (1-5, the five points of plausibility rating). Horizontal axis reflects the number of stages.

Figure 4. Bias Against Disconfirmatory Evidence (BADE) — change Scores in stages 2 to 6, following Moritz and Woodward (2006), figure 1.

Supplementary Material

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: JTC_Appendix 4_cued trials.doc](#)

Supplementary Material

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